

Attack Synthesis in Discrete Event Systems Under Asymmetric Observation Setting[★]

Ruotian Liu^{*}, Wei Duan^{**}, Agostino Marcello Mangini^{*},
Maria Pia Fanti^{*}

^{*} *Polytechnic University of Bari, Italy (e-mails: ruotian.liu,
agostinomarcello.mangini, mariapia.fanti@poliba.it).*

^{**} *Xidian University, China (e-mail: weiduan1103@outlook.com).*

Abstract: This work addresses the problem of cyber attack synthesis in discrete event systems modeled by finite state automata. A malicious attacker may modify an observation outputted from the considered system to confuse an operator who receives either the original observation or the corrupted observation of the system. Particularly, we assume that the attacker has fewer observable events than the operator, resulting in an asymmetric observation setting. This means that the attacker can only deduce the state estimation of the system based on its own observable events, not the observable event set of the system. A relation is defined as a pair of state estimations consistent with the original observation and corrupted observation from the attacker’s perspective. A potentially harmful relation implies that the operator is confused in estimating the given critical states. This work aims to synthesize an attack to establish a potentially harmful relation while maintaining stealthiness. The attack synthesis problem is then considered as a two-player game structure between the operator and the attacker. Finally, an attack graph is constructed to illustrate all possible attack scenarios, and examples are provided to demonstrate the proposed attack strategy.

Keywords: Discrete event system, automaton, attack synthesis, asymmetric observation setting

1. INTRODUCTION

Cyber physical systems (CPSs) integrate sensing, control and networking into physical processes, in which network communication makes the system vulnerable to various network attacks, such as sensor reading corruption and actuator command alteration (Duo et al., 2022; Fritz and Zhang, 2023). Security privacy under such attack scenarios of CPSs has attracted much attention in the community of discrete event systems (DESSs): mainly concerning the problems of attack detection (Carvalho et al., 2018; Alves et al., 2022), attack synthesis (Su, 2018; Tai et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2023), state estimation (Zhang et al., 2021; Li et al., 2023).

This work focuses on the problem of attack synthesis in DESSs. Inspired from the recent work (Tong et al., 2018; Duan et al., 2023) about the current state opacity enforcement under incomparable observation, i.e., different observation inclusion setting exists between the system (supervisor) and passive attacker, we tackle two main points: (i) from an attacker’s viewpoint, a malicious attacker could corrupt an observation outputted from the considered sys-

tem in the communication channel, to confuse an operator that receives the observation of the system, and reach some critical states, i.e., the critical state is considered to be a state that holds some confidential information of the system, which should not be deduced by the illegal user; (ii) concerning an asymmetric observation setting, where the attacker has fewer observable events than the operator, such that the state estimation of the operator and the attacker may be different by deducing their own observable events. The second point is more practical due to the consideration of the limited capability of the attacker.

In this work, the particular attack model we adopt, among those that have been presented in the literature, is based on the one considered by Zhang et al. (2021); Carvalho et al. (2018). Specifically, a set of compromised events that can be corrupted by the attacker is included in the observable event set of the system. To tackle the attack synthesis problem, our approach is similar to studies (Meira-Góes et al., 2020; Yao et al., 2024) that employ a discrete structure to model the game-like interaction between the supervisor (operator) and the attacker, which incorporates all possible attacks. **To our best knowledge, all the mentioned approaches solve the problem by assuming that the same capability of observation between the supervisor and the attacker, which is different from the asymmetric observation setting considered in this work.** The main contribution of the work contains two aspects. First, we extend the asymmetric observation setting into the attack aspect. Second, we construct an attack graph that enumerates all the possible attacks to confuse the

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system. By designing such an attack strategy, our goal is to allow the engineers to detect the attack in terms of potential vulnerabilities from an attacker's viewpoint.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces some basic concepts on the automaton. In Section 3, we formulate the attack synthesis problem. Section 4 mainly presents the strategy to synthesize the attack graph that enumerates all the attack possibilities to achieve the attacker's goal. Finally, conclusions and future works are presented in Section 5.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Let E be a finite set of events and E^* denote the set of all finite length strings over E , including the empty string ε . The length of a string s is the number of events in s , denoted by $|s|$ and the length of empty string is denoted by $|\varepsilon| = 0$. A language $L \subseteq E^*$ is a subset of finite-length strings. A prefix of a string $s \in E^*$ is a string u such that there exists a string v satisfying $uv = s$, in which uv represents the concatenation of two strings u and v . The prefix closure of s is the set of all its prefixes, given by the set $\bar{s} = \{u \in E^* \mid \exists v \in E^*, uv = s\}$.

In this work, we model a DES as a deterministic finite automaton (DFA)¹ $G = (Q, E, f, q_0)$, where Q is a set of states, E is a set of events, $f : Q \times E \rightarrow Q$ is the partial transition function, and $q_0 \in Q$ is the initial state. The transition function f can be extended to $Q \times E^* \rightarrow Q$ in the usual manner: $f(q, \sigma s) = f(f(q, \sigma), s)$ for $q \in Q$, $\sigma \in E$, and $s \in E^*$. Note that $f(q, \varepsilon) = q$ and $f(q, \sigma s)$ is undefined if $f(q, \sigma)$ is undefined. The generated language of DFA G , denoted by $L(G)$, is defined as $L(G) = \{s \in E^* \mid f(q_0, s) \text{ is defined}\}$.

Due to the partial observation of the system G , its event set E is divided as $E = E_o \cup E_{uo}$, where E_o and E_{uo} denote the set of observable events and the set of unobservable events, respectively. The natural projection with respect to E_o is defined as: $P : E^* \rightarrow E_o^*$, where $P(\varepsilon) = \varepsilon$, $P(\sigma) = \sigma$ if $\sigma \in E_o$; $P(\sigma) = \varepsilon$ if $\sigma \in E_{uo}$. It holds $P(\sigma s) = P(\sigma)P(s)$ where $\sigma \in E$ and $s \in E^*$.

Given a system $G = (Q, E, f, q_0)$ and an observation $\omega \in E_o^*$, the set of states consistent with this observation with respect to P starting from a subset of states $Q' \subseteq Q$ is defined as $R_o(Q', \omega) = \{q' \in Q \mid \exists q \in Q', \exists s \in E^* : P(s) = \omega, f(q, s) = q'\}$. The system observer is used to capture the current state estimation of the system, and is defined as: $\mathbf{O}_o = (Q_o, E_o, f_o, q_o^0)$, where $Q_o \subseteq 2^Q$ is the state space, $q_o^0 = R_o(\{q_0\}, \varepsilon)$ is the set of initial states, and $f_o : Q_o \times E_o^* \rightarrow Q_o$ is the transition function.

3. STEALTHY ATTACK UNDER ASYMMETRIC OBSERVATION SETTING

We consider that there exists a subset of *critical states* $Q_C \subseteq Q$ in the system, i.e., such states hold the confidential information of the system, such that the external attacker may intend to access them illegally. In this section, we first define an asymmetric observation setting

¹ The result presented in our work can be easily extended into a nondeterministic case by the mentioned approach in Cassandras and Lafortune (2010).

between the operator and the attacker that may lead the different state estimations following the system behavior. Then an attack model in terms of compromised events is introduced to capture the corruption of the event sequence in the system. Finally, we formulate the attack problem by presenting a potentially harmful relation as the potential attack goal.

3.1 Asymmetric Observation Setting

The main scheme of a system under attack is given as shown in Fig. 1, where an external attacker could modify an observation outputted from the considered system, to confuse an operator that receives the original or corrupted observation of the system. That's because the modification caused by the attacker is performed in the communication channel between the system and the operator. Specifically, the attacker can observe a subset of observable events $E_A \subseteq E_o$, while the operator of the system can observe a subset of observable events $E_P \subseteq E_o$. In this work, by taking into account the limited capability of the attacker in reality, we assume that attacker and operator have the full knowledge of the system structure and the attacker has less observation ability than the operator, i.e., $E_A \subseteq E_P$. For instance, given a system G and an event sequence s , an observation ω obtained by the natural projection $P(s)$, can be altered into ω' according to the attacker's goal and its ability. By this setting, from their own perspectives, the state estimations of the system based on a generated event sequence by the system are possibly different.

Fig. 1. The scheme of the system under attack and asymmetric observation setting.

Example 1. Let us consider the system $G = (Q, E, f, q_0)$ as shown in Fig. 2, where the set of observable events $E_o = \{a, b, c\}$ and the set of critical states $Q_C = \{6\}$. Assume that the attacker can observe the subset of observable events $E_A = \{b, c\}$ and the operator has the same observable event set with the system $E_P = E_o = \{a, b, c\}$. Due to $E_A \subsetneq E_P$, they may refer to different states following some generated sequences of the system. For instance, if the system generates a sequence abc , the attacker can infer that the system is in the set of states $\{6, 7\}$ since only events b and c are observable for itself while the operator could deduce that the system is in the state $\{6\}$.

Fig. 2. A system $G = (Q, E, f, q_0)$.

3.2 Attack Model

Let $E_{com} \subseteq E_o$ be the set of *compromised events* that can be corrupted by the attacker. Subsequently, we consider

$E_{com} \subseteq E_A$ due to the ability of observation of the attacker $E_A \subseteq E_o$. This assumption is more practical compared with the existing studies in the literature. For instance, the events not belonging to E_A but in the event set E_o cannot be observed by the attacker such that no any attack action or modification can be performed. Without loss of generality, we assume that $E_A = E_{com}$ in this work for the sake of brevity. We define the attack projection as $P_A : E_o^* \rightarrow E_A^*$ where $P_A(\varepsilon) = \varepsilon$, $P_A(\beta) = \beta$ if $\beta \in E_A$; $P_A(\beta) = \varepsilon$ if $\beta \in E_o \setminus E_A$. It holds $P_A(\beta\omega) = P_A(\beta)P_A(\omega)$ where $\beta \in E_o$ and $\omega \in E_o^*$.

In this work, an attack is modeled by a function that associates an observable event to a unique observation, i.e., original or compromised event(s), which is formally defined in the following part.

Definition 2. An attack is defined by a function $f_A : E_o \rightarrow E_o^*$ such that for $\beta \in E_o \setminus E_A$, $f_A(\beta) = \beta$; and for $\gamma \in E_A$, we have $f_A(\gamma) = \gamma_I\gamma$ if γ_I is inserted before γ ; $f_A(\gamma) = \varepsilon$ if γ is erased; $f_A(\gamma) = \gamma_R$ if γ is replaced with γ_R , where $\gamma_R \in E_A$ and $\gamma_I \in E_A^*$.

This definition presents a general attack model of the system. For more details on the different types of attacks with consideration of limited attack budget or damage infliction, we refer to the study (Tai et al., 2023). The attack function can also be extended into an event sequence as $f_A(\varepsilon) = \varepsilon$ and $f_A(\omega\beta) = f_A(\omega)f_A(\beta)$ with $\omega \in E_o^*$ and $\beta \in E_o$.

Definition 3. Given a system G with the natural protection P and the attack protection P_A , an attack f_A is said to be *stealthy* if for all observations $\omega \in P(L(G))$, it holds $P_A(f_A(\omega)) \subseteq P_A(\omega)$.

Precisely, from the attacker's viewpoint, stealthiness requires that the set of corrupted observations is contained in the set of observations without attacks. This guarantees that the occurrence of attacks cannot be distinguished from the system behavior in the attacker's perspective.

Example 4. Continue the Example 1 with the system G and event sequence abc , attack f_A replaces b and c with c and b respectively, such that we obtain an observation cb from the attacker's viewpoint as event a is unobservable for the attacker. Since observation cb does not exist in the system behavior observed by the attacker, we say that such attack is not stealthy.

3.3 State Estimation by System and Attacker

In this work, we assume that the operator has the same observable events as the system, i.e., $E_P = E_o$ for simplicity, such that they have the same observer.

To deduce the state estimation from the perspective of attacker, we define the set of possible states starting from a set of states $Q'_o \subseteq Q_o$, $R_A(Q'_o, \omega) = \{q'_A \in Q_o \mid \exists q_A \in Q'_o, \exists s \in E_o^* : P_A(s) = \omega, f_A(q_A, s) = q'_A\}$. The attacker observer is denoted by \mathbf{O}_A and defined as follows. For the set of events in $E_o \setminus E_A$, we perform a self-loop in \mathbf{O}_A to react to each event generated from the system behavior.

Definition 5. (Attacker observer). Given a system $G = (Q, E, f, q_0)$ with $E = E_o \cup E_{uo}$, the attacker observer is defined as $\mathbf{O}_A = (Q_A, E_A, f_A, q_A^0)$, where $Q_A \subseteq 2^{Q_o} \subseteq 2^{2^{Q_o}}$ is the state space, E_A is the set of observable events,

$q_A^0 = R_A(\{q_0\}, \varepsilon)$ is the set of initial states, and $f_A : Q_A \times E_A \rightarrow Q_A$ is the transition relation defined for $q_A \in Q_A$ and $\beta \in E_A$ as $f_A(q_A, \beta) = R_A(q_A, \beta)$. In addition, a self-loop is added for all events unobserved by the attacker at each state.

Definition 6. (Attacked observer). Given a system $G = (Q, E, f, q_0)$ with respect to E_A and f_A , an attacked observer is built by $\mathbf{O}_H = (Q_H, E_H, f_H, q_H^0)$ where $Q_H = Q_A$ is the state space, $q_H^0 = q_A^0$ is the set of initial states, $E_H = E_A$ is the set of events, and f_H is the attack function that modifies the outputted event as $f_H(q_H, f_A(\gamma)) = f_A(q_H, f_A(\gamma))$ for $q_H \in Q_H$ and $\gamma \in E_A$ if $f_A(\gamma)$ is defined; and $f_H(q_H, \beta) = q_H$ for $\beta \in E_o \setminus E_H$. In addition, a self-loop is added for all events unobserved by the attacker at each state.

Thus, the transition function $f_H(q_H, f_A(\gamma))$ ensures that the attacked observer contains all attacked operations to react to every event observed by the attacker, and to add a self-loop for all events unobserved by the attacker.

Example 7. Continue the Example 1 with the system G (see Fig. 2), a system observer \mathbf{O}_o is given in Fig. 3(a) while its attacker observer \mathbf{O}_A and attacked observer \mathbf{O}_H is displayed in Fig. 3(b). Given an event sequence abc generated by the system, following the attacked observer \mathbf{O}_H , we know that event a is added as a self-loop at initial state since it is not observed by the attacker; observation bc could be corrupted into cc . Consequently, the attacker estimates that the system is entering a non-critical state $\{7\}$, while the operator also deduces that the system is also in the state $\{7\}$ due to the asymmetric setting, resulting in the confusion to operator since it could deduce the critical state $\{6\}$ based on the original observation in reality. Here we rename states $\{\{1\}, \{2\}\}$, $\{\{3, 5\}, \{4\}\}$, and $\{\{6\}, \{7\}\}$ as A, B and C , respectively, for later use.

Fig. 3. (a) System observer \mathbf{O}_o (b) Attacker and attacked observers \mathbf{O}_A and \mathbf{O}_H .

3.4 Problem formulation

An attack without a specific goal is meaningless. In this part, we first present the attacker's goal that we are focusing on. Inspired by the work in Zhang et al. (2021), which introduces a misleading relation to capture whether a given pair of state estimations from the original and corrupted observations could be reached under attack, this work focuses on a different relation with two main distinctions. First, we examine a pair of state estimations from

the attacker's viewpoint, considering both the attacker observer and attacked observer. Secondly, the attacker's goal differs. Specifically, the proposed attack strategy aims to confuse the operator in two scenarios: i) when a critical state is potentially reached based on the original observation, the attacker cannot deduce it from the corrupted observation, ensuring the operator's inability to deduce it due to the asymmetric observation setting; ii) when a critical state has not been reached, the operator might mistakenly believe that the secret has been attained based on the corrupted observation.

Definition 8. Given a system $G = (Q, E, f, q_0)$ and a set of critical states Q_C , a relation is defined as a state estimation pair $(R_A(\{q_A^0\}, \omega), R_A(\{q_A^0\}, \omega')) \in \mathcal{R}$, where $\mathcal{R} \subseteq 2^Q \times 2^Q$, ω is the **correct** observation and ω' is the corrected observation. A relation in \mathcal{R} is said to be *potentially harmful* if there exists $\omega \in P_A(L(G))$, $f_A(\omega) = \omega'$ satisfying one of the following conditions:

$$\begin{cases} (i) R_A(\{q_A^0\}, \omega) \cap Q_C \neq \emptyset \wedge R_A(\{q_A^0\}, \omega') \cap Q_C = \emptyset \\ (ii) R_A(\{q_A^0\}, \omega) \cap Q_C = \emptyset \wedge R_A(\{q_A^0\}, \omega') \cap Q_C \neq \emptyset \end{cases}$$

Remark 9. Our approach considers the attacker's limited observation capabilities compared to the operator. Damage occurs if the operator observes a critical state from the original observation in case (i), or if the operator observes a critical state from the corrupted observation in case (ii). **In the worst-case scenario, the operator's state estimation aligns with non-critical states consistent with both the original and corrupted observations.**

Definition 10. Consider the system G with the set of critical states Q_C , an attack f_A is said to be *valid* if it is stealthy and there exists a potentially harmful relation.

In the rest of this work, we address the following attack synthesis problem:

Problem: Given a system $G = (Q, E, f, q_0)$ and a set of critical states Q_C , we aim to synthesize a valid attack.

4. SYNTHESIZE AN ATTACK GRAPH

The basic idea of this work is to construct an *attack graph* that contains all attack possibilities for guaranteeing the attacker's goals. To do so, we first assume that the attacker observes (but cannot react to) events in $E_o \setminus E_A$, and build a two-players attack game structure, where the players are the system (or the operator since they have the same observable event set in this work) and the attacker, to systematically illustrate how the attacker could corrupt the observation following the system behavior. Then, we remove the above assumption that events in $E_o \setminus E_A$ are observed, and trim some problematic states that violate the attack goals. Finally, an attack graph is built by merging the states in the trimmed attack game structure, which is proposed by an algorithm.

4.1 Attack Game Structure

Definition 11. Consider a system $G = (Q, E, f, q_0)$ with a set of critical states Q_C , and its system observer $\mathbf{O}_o = (Q_o, E_o, f_o, q_o^0)$, attacker observer $\mathbf{O}_A = (Q_A, E_A, f_A, q_A^0)$, attacked observer $\mathbf{O}_H = (Q_H, E_H, f_H, q_H^0)$. An attack game structure is defined as $\mathcal{AS} = (V, E_o, \delta, v_o)$, where

- $V = V_S \cup V_A$, where $V_S = Q_o \times Q_A \times Q_H$ is the set of structure states and $V_A = (Q_o \times Q_A \times Q_H) \times E_o$ is the set of attacked states;
- E_o is the set of events;
- $v_o = (q_o^0, q_A^0, q_H^0) \in V_S$ is the initial state;
- $\delta = \delta_{SA} \cup \delta_{AS}$ is the transition function, where
 - (1) $\delta_{SA} = V_S \times E_o \rightarrow V_A$ is the transition function from the system to the attacker that is defined as $\forall (q_o, q_A, q_H) \in V_S, \forall \alpha \in E_o, \delta_{SA}((q_o, q_A, q_H), \alpha) = ((f_o(q_o, \alpha), f_A(q_A, \alpha), q_H), \alpha)$ if both $f_o(q_o, \alpha)$ and $f_A(q_A, \alpha)$ are defined.
 - (2) $\delta_{AS} = V_A \times E_o^{\leq K+1} \rightarrow V_S$ is the transition function from the attacker to the system that is defined as $\forall ((q_o, q_A, q_H), \alpha) \in V_A, \forall \alpha \in E_A$ and $\omega \in E_A^*$, it holds that (i) $\delta_{AS}(((q_o, q_A, q_H), \alpha), \omega) = ((f_o(q_o, \alpha), f_A(q_A, \alpha), q_H), \alpha)$ if both $f_o(q_o, \alpha)$ and $f_A(q_A, \alpha)$ are defined; (ii) $\forall ((q_o, q_A, q_H), \alpha) \in V_A$ where $\alpha \in E_o \setminus E_A$, we have $\delta_{AS}(((q_o, q_A, q_H), \alpha), \omega) = ((q_o, q_A, f_H(q_H, \omega)))$.

If the system generates an event observed by the attacker, $E_o^{\leq K+1}$ represents all the possible attacks including replacement, deletion and finite insertion with transition function δ_{AS} . Otherwise, the attack is assumed to "react" with the same event generated by the system. The attack game structure \mathcal{AS} contains all possible actions between the system and the attacker.

Remark 12. Attack game structure \mathcal{AS} is obtained by the product of system, attacker and attacked observers since we assume $E_P = E_o$ for simplicity (see Section 3.3), such that the system observer is the same as the operator observer. In a general case that $E_P \subseteq E_o$, \mathcal{AS} could also be obtained by taking into account the additional operator observer within the product.

Example 13. Continue the Example 7 with the system G shown in Fig. 2, system observer \mathbf{O}_o , attacker observer \mathbf{O}_A and attacked observer \mathbf{O}_H in Fig. 3. Following Definition 11, the attack game structure \mathcal{AS} is partially presented in Fig. 4. Note that in this example we only consider the replacement and deletion attacks for simplicity.

Fig. 4. Partial attack game structure.

To guarantee the valid attack synthesis, we need to remove some states in \mathcal{AS} when the attacker may not be able to react to one or more events generated by the system; or

Fig. 5. Trimmed attack game structure.

the operator and attacker both infer that the current state may be entering a critical state that leads to the violation of potentially harmful relation. The following definition characterizes the problematic states.

Definition 14. Give an attack game structure $\mathcal{AS} = (V, E_o, \delta, v_o)$, a state v in V is said to be *problematic* if one of the following three conditions is satisfied:

- $$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (i) [\exists q \in Q_H \cup Q_A, q \cap Q_C \neq \emptyset, (q_A, q_H) \text{ is not} \\ \quad \text{potentially harmful}] \wedge [v \in V_S]; \\ (ii) [\exists q \in Q_o, q \text{ is tagged as duplicated, } (q_A, q_H) \\ \quad \text{is not potentially harmful}] \wedge [v \in V_S]; \\ (iii) [\forall \omega \in E_A^*, \delta_{SA}(v, \omega) \text{ is undefined}] \wedge [v \in V_A]. \end{array} \right.$$

By following Definition 14, three types of problematic states possibly exist in the attack game structure. The first two conditions are verified if for a state $(q_o, q_A, q_H) \in V_S$, there exists a state $q \in Q_H \cup Q_A$ (resp., Q_o) satisfying $q \cap Q_C \neq \emptyset$ (resp., is duplicated state). Moreover, the state estimation pair (q_A, q_H) is not potentially harmful such that the attack is not valid by Definition 10. The third condition is satisfied if for all attack actions the function δ_{SA} is not defined, which implies that the attacker can not react the event. For more details about the technique of trimming the problematic states, we refer the reader to the study in Duan et al. (2023). By trimming all the problematic states, we obtain a trimmed attack game structure that is denoted as $\mathcal{TAS} = (V_T, E_o, \delta, v_0)$, in which V_T is the state structure. In the following, we show such procedure in the example.

Example 15. Given a system $G = (Q, E, f, q_0)$ and a set of critical states $Q_C = \{6\}$, the trimmed attack game structure is obtained by removing all the problematic states as shown in Fig. 5. For instance, the state $[\{7\}, C, C]$ is problematic since its states q_A and q_H do not respect the potentially harmful relation \mathcal{R} , i.e., $q_A = C = \{6, 7\} \cap Q_C \neq \emptyset$ and $q_H = C = \{6, 7\} \cap Q_C \neq \emptyset$. In other word, the attacker does not attempt to confuse the operator based on the corrupted observation.

4.2 Attack Graph

An attack graph $AG = (V_E, E_A, \delta_A \cup \delta_S, v_0^E)$ is built by merging states from the trimmed attack game structure \mathcal{TAS} , where V_E is the set of states, E_A is the set of

observable events, δ_A and δ_S are the transition functions that evolve the states in the attack graph, v_0^E is the initial state. This attack graph is used to ensure that all attack options are defined at the merged states, which is required by the stealthiness. In the following, we present an algorithm to construct an attack graph that enumerates all the possible valid attacks.

Algorithm 1: Construction of an attack graph

Input: $\mathcal{TAS} = (V_T, E_o, \delta, v_0)$, $V_T = V'_N \cup V'_F$, and $\delta = \delta_{AP} \cup \delta_{PA}$

Output: $AG = (V_E, E_A, \delta_A \cup \delta_S, v_0^E)$, where $V_E = V_m \cup V_n$

- 1 $v_0^E = \{v_0\} \cup \{v \in V'_F \mid \exists \sigma \in (E_o \setminus E_A)^* : \delta(v_0, \sigma) = v\}$;
 - 2 Initialize $V_E = V_m = \{v_0^E\}$, and $V_n = \emptyset$;
 - 3 **for** $v \in V_m$ that have not been tagged **do**
 - 4 **for** $\gamma \in E_A$ **do**
 - 5 **if** $\exists z \in v, \delta_A(z, \gamma)$ is defined **then**
 - 6 $\delta(v, \gamma) = \bigcup_{z \in v} \delta_A(z, \gamma) = \{y \in V'_F \mid \exists \sigma \in E_o^* : P_A(\sigma) = \gamma \wedge y \in \delta(z, \sigma)\}$;
 - 7 Add $\delta_A(v, \gamma)$ to V_n ;
 - 8 **for** $v \in V_n$ that have not been tagged **do**
 - 9 **for** $\omega \in E_A^*$ **do**
 - 10 **if** $\forall z \in v, \delta_S(z, \omega)$ is defined **then**
 - 11 $\delta(v, \omega) = \bigcup_{z \in v} \delta_S(z, \omega) = \bigcup_{z \in v} \delta_{PA}(z, \omega)$;
 - 12 Add $\delta_S(v, \omega)$ to V_m ;
 - 13 **Go back to line 3 and repeat until all accessible part has been built;**
-

We briefly explain how Algorithm 1 works here. We first compute the initial state of the attack graph v_0^E in step 1 as the set of states that can be reached from state v_0 in trimmed game structure via sequences of events unobserved by the attacker. For the sake of explanation, we assume that $v_0^E = \{v_0, v_1\}$. Then steps 3 to 10 evolve the initial state v_0^E to a new state $v_1^E \in V_m$ via δ_A , where $\sigma \in E_o^*$ since the attacker outputs the same event if the system generates an event unobserved by the attacker, v'_0 and v'_1 are system states in V_S . Subsequently, steps 8 to 12 evolve the state v_1^E to a new state $v_2^E \in V_n$ via δ_S .

Theorem 16. Given a system $G = (Q, E, f, q_0)$ and a set of critical states Q_C , an attack f_A is valid if and only if

it is synthesized by the attack graph $AG = (V_E, E_A, \delta_A \cup \delta_S, v_0^E)$ that is constructed by Algorithm 1.

Proof. (If) By contradiction, we assume that the attack is not valid. That is, at least one of the conditions in Definition 10 does not hold. Thus, it cannot react to every event observed by the attacker or it cannot modify sequences generated by the system to attack sequences such that the relation is not potentially harmful. In other words, one can find a sequence leading to states that satisfies the problematic state. However, by construction of trimmed attack game structure, such sequences have been removed. Furthermore, suppose the attacker cannot ensure that every attacked sequence can be recognized by the system; however, this is not allowed in attack graph, which is a contradiction. Therefore, the attack should be valid if it is synthesized by the attack graph.

(Only If) Given a valid attack, the condition of Definition 10 holds. Thus, it can be retained in attack game structure since we build \mathcal{AS} by following system behavior observed by the attacker. Moreover, we prune away all problematic states when we build trimmed one such that the potentially harmful relation holds. Finally, the transition function in attack graph is able to ensure that every attacked operation can be recognized by the system. Therefore, all the attack sequences exist in attack graph, such that any subsequent attacked sequence can maintain the previous conditions. We can conclude that the attack can be synthesized by the attack graph. \diamond

Example 17. Consider the system G in Fig. 2, the attack graph demonstrated in Fig. 6 is obtained by Algorithm 1. For an event sequence abc generated by the system, the attacker can deduce the set of states $C = \{6, 7\}$ containing the critical state $\{6\}$. The attacker could respond to b via a replacement with the observation c and hold the original observation c , such that the operator certainly infers the non-critical state $\{7\}$ while damage occurs since its original state estimation is included in the state $\{6\}$. For an event sequence bdc , the attacker also could deduce the set of states $C = \{6, 7\}$. In such a case, the attacker cannot make confusion to the operator by the same attack actions since the operator could also deduce the non-critical state from the original sequence. As mentioned before, the potentially harmness implies that the attacker attempts to make confusion to the operator by its own limited capability observation.

Fig. 6. Attack graph.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we address the problem of attack synthesis in discrete event systems under asymmetric information observation settings. We define a potentially harmful relation as a pair of state estimations consistent with both original and corrupted sequences. The notion of a valid attack is introduced to characterize the attacker's capability to confuse the system. Subsequently, we construct an attack graph using a game scheme to explore all possible attacks ensuring the attacker's goal and stealthiness. This involves trimming problematic states and merging others. Future work will investigate more general cases where no inclusion relation exists between the operator and attacker, and will also address the [optimization of attack operations](#).

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